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D1: Report on the development and performance of the prototype emission reference material (ERM), demonstrating an emission profile that decreases by less than 10 % over at least 14 days, including information about the reservoir materials, source strength, mass transport modelling, and the results of emissions tests

Lead partner: **FhG**

Other partners: BAM, POLITO, TUBITAK, ZAG

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1 Development of VOC polymeric reservoirs based on encapsulation

The aim of this part of the work package was to develop an encapsulation process for the synthesis of different polymer-based microcapsules loaded with various pre-selected volatile organic compounds (VOC). Five types of relevant VOCs, such as limonene, pinene, toluene, hexane, and hexadecane were selected and used as a “core” material in the encapsulation process. The formulation of capsules was achieved through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation at the oil-water droplet’s interface.

For each VOC the encapsulation process was established and optimised taking into consideration the physicochemical characteristics of encapsulated material. Different process parameters, such as type and amount of monomer, type and amount of surfactant and phase ratio have been tested to find the optimal conditions for the efficient production of stable microcapsules with a permeable shell and high encapsulation yield of VOC. The obtained capsules were characterised in terms of colloidal stability, particle size, size distribution and morphology. The most promising samples were selected and sent to the project partners for further characterisation of chemical composition, encapsulation efficiency, porosity and emission. The results provided by partners are presented in **section 1.3** “Emission testing of VOC polymeric reservoirs based on encapsulation” and **chapter 3** “Characterisation of the polymer capsules”.

1.1 Experimental details

1.1.1 Materials

All chemicals used within the project were of analytical grade and used as received without further purification. D-limonene (96 %, [5989-27-5], Thermoscientific), α -pinene (98 %, [80-56-8], Aldrich), toluene (99.9 %, [108-88-3], VWR Chemicals), *n*-hexane (≥ 99 %, [110-54-3], VWR Chemicals), *n*-hexadecane (99 %, [544-76-3], Alfa Aesar), glycerin (99 %, [56-81-5], abcr GmbH & Co. KG), 1,6-hexanediol (HD, [629-11-8], 99 %, Sigma-Aldrich), 1,6-hexanediamine (HMDA, [124-09-4], Merck), isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI, 98 %, [4098-71-9], Acros-Organics), tolylene 2,4-diisocyanate (TDI, 95 %, [584-84-9], Sigma-Aldrich), TUBASSIST®FIX 157W (Tub, CHT R. BEITLICH GmbH) is a solvent-free commercial product based on hexamethylene diisocyanate oligomers; dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTL, 95 %, [77-58-7], Sigma-Aldrich), carboxymethyl cellulose sodium salt, (CMC, [9004-32-4], Sigma-Aldrich), medium viscosity, average, $M_v \sim 250,000$ g/mol; 0.60–0.95 substitution. Surfactants: polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, M_w 31000 g/mol, ≥ 99.5 %, [9002-89-5], Sigma Aldrich) and sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS, 98 %, [151-21-3], Acros organics). Ultra-pure water (Thermo Scientific™) was used throughout the experimental runs.

1.1.2 Preparation of capsules

The VOC loaded capsules were prepared by a polyaddition/polycondensation reaction performed at the oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion droplet's interface. The process and chemical reactions are schematically shown in **Figure 1**. The droplets were generated using membrane emulsification, employing a microporous membrane composed of Shirasu porous glass (SPG). For the formation of capsules with an average size of 15 μm and 50 μm the SPG membrane with the pore size of 5.1 and 9.9 μm was used respectively.

The dispersed phase, consisting of VOC, DBTL (in some runs) and isocyanate(s) was pressed through the membrane, forming droplets at the pore mouths on the surface of the membrane contacted by the continuous phase. The continuous phase consists of surfactant(s) aqueous solution. The details regarding the compositions of two phases are summarised in **Table 1–3**.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of VOC encapsulation through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation reaction.

1.1.3 Characterisation of capsules

The average size of oil in water (O/W) droplets was analysed by optical microscope Olympus BX60. The average size and the size distribution of capsules were determined from scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images using the software ImageJ for the analysis and retracing the shape of capsules. The morphology of formulated capsules was studied by SEM using LEO (Zeiss) 1550 VP at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. A drop of diluted sample was deposited on a silicon wafer and dried at room temperature. The samples were covered with a thin layer

The first series of experiments was done with all VOCs and the SPG membrane having an average pore size of 5.1 μm . According to the producer this type of membrane results in droplets with an average size of 15 μm . For bigger capsules (50 μm in diameter), the SPG membrane with a pore size of 9.9 μm was employed. Depending on VOC and its properties (density, miscibility with water and isocyanate(s), interfacial VOC/water tension) the optimisation of the synthesis parameters had to be done for each VOC. Within the reporting period we performed the optimisation of capsule synthesis using limonene as VOC. The main parameter for the optimisation includes the variation in monomer ratio and type of isocyanate. For large capsules the use of TDI (which is more reactive compared to IPDI) leads to better results, i.e., more stable and more homogeneous in size. The use of higher amounts of monomer results in capsules with a thicker shell. However, the emission rate was not reduced, confirming that the size of pores was not smaller.

The chemical composition and average size of successful samples are summarised in **Table 1** (for limonene), **Table 2** (for toluene) and **Table 3** (for pinene, hexane and hexadecane). The morphology of produced capsules was studied by SEM and the images of selected samples are shown in **Figure 2**.

Table 1. Chemical composition and average size of capsules loaded with limonene.

Sample name	Limonene [ml]	Crosslinker	Hydrophilic monomer	Surfactant	Capsule size
<i>SPG membrane 5.1 μm</i>					
HIL_1	5	IPDI 1.5 g / DBTL 12 μl	hexanediol, 0.8 g	40 ml PVP, 5 wt% + 20 mg LigS + 20 g H ₂ O	no complete encapsulation
HIL_2		IPDI 1.5 g / DBTL 12 μl	hexanediol, 0.8 g	40 ml PVP, 1 wt%	
HIL_3		IPDI 1.5 g / Tub 0.2 g	hexanediol, 0.8 g	40 ml PVP, 1 wt%	
HIL_4		IPDI 1.0 g / Tub 0.2 g	hexanediol, 0.8 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	encapsulation yield between 50–60 %
HIL_5		IPDI 1.0 g / Tub 0.2 g	hexanediol, 0.5 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	
GTIL_1	4.7	IPDI 0.92 g / Tub 0.2 g	glycerin, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	16 \pm 4 μm
HDTIL_1		IPDI 0.92 g / Tub 0.2 g	HMDA, 0.5 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	21 \pm 10 μm
HDTL_1		Tub 0.4 g	HMDA, 0.25 g	40 ml SDS, 0.3 wt%	10 \pm 5 μm
HTL_1		Tub 0.4 g	hexanediol, 0.25 g	40 ml SDS, 0.3 wt%	9 \pm 4 μm
HDTDTL1	4.0	TDI 0.2 g / Tub 0.2 g	hexanediol, 0.15 g	40 ml LigS, 2 wt%	11 \pm 9 μm
GTIL_108/109A		IPDI 0.6 g / Tub 0.15 / DBTL 6 μl	glycerin, 0.14 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	n.d.
HDTIL_109Bu			HMDA, 0.15 g		24 \pm 6 μm

GTIL_109Cu	2.1		glycerin, 0.11 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	n.d.
GTIL_109Co					n.d.
GTIL_109D					n.d.
GTIL_110Au					43±8 µm
GTIL_110Ao					41±6 µm
GTIL_110Bo					n.d.
<i>SPG membrane 9.9 µm</i>					
GTIL_112A	2.1	IPDI 0.75 g / Tub 0.25 g / DBTL 6 µl	glycerin, 0.12 g	60 ml PVA, 1 wt%	many polymer particles, no capsules
STIL_114A	2.0	IPDI 0.6 g / Tub 0.13 g / DBTL 5 µl	sucrose, 0.04 g	40 ml PVP, 5 wt% + 20 mg LigS + 20 g H ₂ O	no stable system, encapsulation yield < 60 %
STIL_116A				60 ml PVP, 5 wt%	18±8 µm
HDTIL_120A	4.3	IPDI 1.2 g / Tub 0.3 g / DBTL 12 µl	HMDA, 0.5 g	120 ml PVA, 1 wt% + SDS 0.2 wt%	58±6 µm
GTIL_120B	4.3		glycerin, 0.4 g		many polymer particles, no capsules
HTTL_126A	2.0	TDI 0.24 g / Tub 0.06 g	hexanediol, 0.16 g	60 ml PVA, 1 wt% + SDS 0.2 wt%	37±7 µm
GTTL_126B			glycerin, 0.1 g		
HDTTL_133A			TDI 0.125 g / Tub 0.125 g		
HDTTL_143	4.0	TDI 0.34 g / Tub 0.17 g	HMDA, 0.5 g	120 ml PVA, 1 wt% + SDS, 0.2 wt%	60±10 µm

n.d. – not determined.

Figure 2. Light microscopy and SEM images of limonene-loaded capsules.

Table 2. Chemical composition and average size of capsules loaded with toluene.

Sample name	Toluene [ml]	Crosslinker	Hydrophilic monomer	Surfactant	Capsule size
SPG membrane 5.1 μm					
HTIT_1	4.7	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.21 g / DBTL, 7.5 μl	hexanediol, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	44 \pm 19 μm
HDTT_2	4.7	Tub, 0.8 g	HMDA, 0.5 g	40 ml SDS, 0.23 wt%	43 \pm 11 μm
GTIT_1	4.7	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.21 g / DBTL, 7.5 μl	glycerin, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	37 \pm 25 μm
HTT_2	4.7	Tub, 0.8 g	hexanediol, 0.5 g	40 ml SDS, 0.23 wt%	many polymer particles, but no capsules
SPG membrane 9.9 μm					
GTIT_2	4.7	IPDI, 1.0 g / Tub, 0.21 g / DBTL, 7.5 μl	glycerin, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	encapsulation efficiency < 20 %
HTIT_2			hexanediol, 0.1 g		

According to the obtained results it can be concluded that capsules with toluene are bigger in size as compared to those made with limonene. The encapsulation efficiency was between 60–90 %.

Figure 3. Light microscopy and SEM images of toluene-loaded capsules.

Table 3. Chemical composition and average size of capsules loaded with different VOC materials.

Sample name	VOC	Crosslinker	Hydrophilic monomer	Surfactant	Capsule size
GTIP_2	pinene, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.2 g	glycerin, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	19±5 µm
HDTIP_1	pinene, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.2 g	HMDA, 0.5 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	23±7 µm

HTIP_1	pinene, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.2 g	hexanediol, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	20±10 µm
HTIH_1	hexane, 9.5 ml	IPDI, 2.4 g / DBTL, 15 µl	hexanediol, 0.2 g	80 ml PVA, 1 wt%	encapsulation efficiency < 20 %
HTIH_2	hexane, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 1.2 g / DBTL, 7.5 µl	hexanediol, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	
HTIH_3	hexane, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 0.92 g / Tub, 0.2 g / DBTL, 7.5 µl	hexanediol, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	many particles, no capsules
GIHD_1	hexadecane, 4.7 ml	IPDI, 1.25 g	glycerin, 0.1 g	40 ml PVA, 1 wt%	encapsulation efficiency < 10 %
HIHD_1			hexanediol, 0.1 g		

Capsules prepared with hexane and hexadecane as VOC were not stable. Total phase separation was observed already during the emulsification when hexadecane was used. With hexane some capsules were obtained, but the recipe and process parameters still need to be optimised to get an efficient yield of encapsulation.

Figure 4. Light microscopy and SEM images of different VOC-loaded capsules.

The “core-shell” morphology could be clearly seen in all analysed samples. The shell thickness mainly depends on the amount and type of used chemicals. In contrast to heptane-loaded capsules, it was not possible to prepare stable and closed capsules using PVP and lignin sulfonate as surfactants with any of the tested

VOCs. Capsules that were colloiddally stable and stable under SEM measurement conditions (under vacuum) were sent for emission testing to JRP partner BAM, and for further characterisation of chemical composition and pore size to partner TUBITAK.

1.3 Emission testing of VOC polymeric reservoirs based on encapsulation

The emission behaviour (i.e., emission rate over time) of different capsules was tested. The capsule samples were provided in the form of aqueous suspensions. Before testing is conducted, usually one millilitre of suspension was transferred into a petri dish. The petri dish was then placed into an emission test chamber.

According to EN 16516, the chamber parameters were set at 23 ± 1 °C, 50 ± 5 % relative humidity (RH) and an air exchange rate of 0.5 h^{-1} . Different chamber sizes were used, but most of the experiments were conducted in 22 L desiccators. The emission rate was used to compare different experiments to each other as the emission rate normalises the chamber air concentration on the dimension of the sample (or its in-weight or concentration) and air exchange rate (see equation below).

$$\text{emission rate} \left[\frac{ng}{g * h} \right] = \frac{\text{concentration in air} \left[\frac{ng}{L} \right]}{\text{in - weight} [g]} * \text{air flow rate} [L/h]$$

Results from the emission testing were used as feedback information for the development of the capsules as changes in the composition of the polymeric material directly influence the emission behaviour.

1.3.1 Emission behaviour of different capsule types

At the beginning, capsules loaded with *n*-heptane, which were synthesised in our preliminary work, were investigated. After drying for approximately 24 h, a steady decrease in concentration can be recognised until a relatively stable phase is reached (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Emission of preliminary capsules from 2019. The incorporated VOC is n-heptane. A steady decrease in emission can be recognised.

The form of the emission curve is quite common for many different materials. When looking at the relatively stable phase (500–840 h), a decrease in emission of about 25 % can be seen. Two goals were defined within the project for the development of new emission reference materials (ERM): (a) a suitable/well-detectable concentration in the test chamber (~100–150 ng/L) and (b) a change of less than 10 % in emission over 14 days. While the preliminary capsule type already emits at about 100 ng/L, the change in emission (25 %) over 14 days is too high. The emission can often be easily adjusted by placing more material into one chamber, so the stability requirement over 14 days is more important. **Table 4** contains all tested capsule samples, produced by partner FhG.

The first batch tested within the project consisted of ten capsule samples, filled with three different VOCs (toluene, pinene and limonene). The chemical compositions of the tested capsules are summarised in **Table 1–3**. A change of 48–73 % over 14 days with an average emission rate of 7–200 ng/g*h was found for the three toluene containing samples (**Table 4**, entry 1–3). A deviation of 44–63 % over 14 days with an average emission rate of 26–76 ng/g*h was found for the three pinene containing samples (**Table 4**, entry 4–6). A deviation of 59–63 % over 14 days with an average emission rate of 301–2108 ng/g*h was found for the two of four limonene containing samples (**Table 4**, entry 7–8). Almost all tested samples showed the typical decrease of emission over time. The samples HDTIL_1 and GTIL_1 exhibited the same initial behaviour, but the emission curve shows a turning point at ~160–190 h followed by an increase of emission (**Table 4**, entry 9–10). To exclude any mistakes during the first testing, the emission experiment was conducted a second time for both samples and quite different results were found (70 vs 147 % increase, and 8 vs 400 % increase over 14 days).

Table 4. Characterisation of capsule emission change over 14 days and average emission rate.

Entry	Sample name	Change [%]	Mean ER [ng/g*h]	VOC
1	HDTT_2	48 (decrease)	7	toluene
2	HTIT_1	73 (decrease)	200	toluene
3	GTIT_1	57 (decrease)	82	toluene
4	HTIP_1	63 (decrease)	26	pinene
5	HDTiP_1	44 (decrease)	76	pinene
6	GTIP_2	56 (decrease)	45	pinene
7	CIL_2A	59 (decrease)	301	limonene
8	HDTDTL_2	63 (decrease)	2108	limonene
9	HDTIL_1	70 (increase) 147 (increase)	170 190	limonene
10	GTIL_1	8 (increase) 400 (increase)	11 80	limonene
11	HDTIL_108-109A	78 (decrease)	478	limonene
12	HDTIL_109Bu	100 (decrease)	171	limonene
13	HDTIL_109Co	100 (decrease)	159	limonene
14	HDTIL_109Cu	84 (decrease)	316	limonene
15	HDTIL_109D	73 (decrease)	737	limonene
16	GTIL_110Ao	87 (decrease)	2610	limonene
17	GTIL_110Au	100 (decrease)	112	limonene
18	GTIL_110Bo	80 (decrease)	827	limonene
19	GTIL_1	89 (decrease)	280	limonene
20	HDTIL_120A	279 (increase)	1580	limonene
21	STIL_116A	80 (decrease)	2250	limonene
22	GTIP_2	100 (decrease)	180	pinene
23	GTIL_1	5 (decrease)	270	limonene
24	HDTIL_120A	14 (decrease)	760	limonene
25	HDTTL_143	10 (decrease)	620	limonene
26	HDTTL_133A	53 (increase) 6 (decrease)	550 330	limonene

It was assumed that the mixing of suspension before the extraction of capsules might have had an influence, because intact and broken capsules rapidly separate by floating and settling respectively. Replicates of the other types did not differ as much as the replicates of HDTIL_1 and GTIL_1.

Moderate changes (44–59 % over 14 days) were found for each VOC. The best result was found during one experiment with GTIL_1 (8 % change over 14 days), which could not be reproduced in a second experiment.

It was found that the synthesis route had to be strongly adapted for each VOC, because of individual interactions between the VOC and the polymeric wall material. Thus, comparisons between different samples can be hardly made on the synthesis/emission information alone. The best three and one additional representative (GTIL_1, HDTIL_1, HDTT_2 and HTIT_1) were sent to partner TUBITAK for further characterisation (see **chapter 3**). The consortium decided to focus on one VOC (limonene) and to investigate the influence of chemical composition and phase ratios first.

The next batch tested contained 11 samples (**Table 4**, entry 11–21). The synthesis was adapted, so that capsules with a thicker polymer shell were produced. It was expected that a thicker shell will result in smaller pore sizes and thus in reduced emission. The average emission from this batch is however higher than the average emission of the former batch. Also, the variability is higher than before (73–100 % decrease or 279 % increase over 14 days). It seems, that the pore size is not directly dependant on the shell thickness.

As a side project, two capsule samples (containing limonene and pinene respectively) with an additional outer gel layer were tested. An additional restriction can be helpful to further reduce and homogenise the emission. In this case, the gel dried within two days and no emission was detectable at all. The control sample (containing pinene) without gel exhibited an emission, which declined to zero within two weeks (**Table 4**, entry 22).

For practical reasons, most of the emission tests were conducted for about two weeks and a similar time window was used to calculate the presented values for each sample. However, the testing duration can have a significant influence on the performance of a material, especially for materials, that have not yet fully reached their stable phase.^[1] A better approach would be to test all specimen for longer durations and only compare the stable phases. Thus, four samples were tested for a prolonged period (up to 60 days) (**Table 4**, entry 23–26).

Figure 6. Both replicate testings of GTIL_1 (A), HDTIL_120A (B), HDTTL_143 (C) and HDTTL_133A (D) are plotted.

Both replicate testings of GTIL_1, HDTIL_120A, HDTTL_143 and HDTTL_133A were plotted for better visualisation of their reproducibility (**Figure 6**). The best and quite reproducible result was obtained for GTIL_1 (5 % change in emission over 14 days with 270 ng/g*h; **Figure 6, A**). As seen before, the samples HDTIL_1 and HDTIL_120A, exhibit a unique emission behaviour (increase after initial phase). After a second, local maximum (~550 h), the emission of HDTIL_120A starts to decrease again, reaching a more stable phase than before (1000–1400 h; 14 % decrease of emission over 14 days; **Figure 6, B**). The most reproducible and a good stability was obtained by testing HDTTL_143 (10 % change in emission over 14 days with 620 ng/g*h; **Figure 6, C**). HDTTL_133A exhibits the worst reproducibility – the values were 6 % decrease and 53 % increase respectively over 14 days, whereas the last two respective datapoints have a significant impact (**Figure 6, D**). A third repetition or an even longer testing period is advised for

this sample. Nonetheless, very good to good results were found (GTIL_1 and HDTTL_143) or indicated (HDTTL_133A).

2 Development of VOC reservoirs based on porous materials

Our second approach for the generation of ERMs is the impregnation of porous materials. Here, porous material and an amount of liquid VOC are placed in an autoclave. The reaction vessel is sealed, and CO₂ is introduced until a certain pressure is reached. Then the autoclave is heated to 32 °C – due to the increase in temperature, the pressure rises accordingly to about 74 bar. At these conditions, CO₂ is in its supercritical state and acts as a solvent for the VOC. The mixture inside the autoclave is stirred and the porous material is treated for a few minutes. Then the pressure and/or temperature is slowly reduced. The impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave and transferred into an emission test chamber for testing. Emission testing and data handling was performed as described before (see **chapter 1.3**).

2.1 Optimisation and influence of impregnation parameters

We used a model material (FD-107) and VOC (*n*-heptane) to test and optimise various impregnation parameters. The properties of the model and other used materials can be found in **Table 5**. It was quickly realised, that FD-107 is hygroscopic, and that no emission can be detected, when the impregnated material was stored, transported, or measured in humid air. Thus, measures were undertaken to avoid or minimise contact with humid air and testing of this material was performed in dry air.

At first, a lot of impregnated model material samples were tested, that were impregnated at standard conditions (74 bar and 32 °C). At these conditions (and above), CO₂ is in a supercritical state. Though good values were found, a lot of testings were necessary to confirm the distribution of changes over 14 days (8–20 %). Every fifth sample did not show any emission at all and a few outliers with changes of 50 % or higher were found. This variability has at least three main contributions coming from the impregnation, testing and contact with water. The experimental skill and thus the effect of measures to avoid water ingress increased at the beginning of our study drastically. Nevertheless, high values were obtained occasionally even then. Considerably higher values originate very likely from contact with water. Unfortunately, the contributions cannot be separated from each other. No outlier correction can be performed, when only a few testings were conducted for a set of parameters, and the values must be evaluated as they are.

Table 5. Properties of used materials.

Material	Pore volume [cm ³ /g]	Pore size [nm]	Form	Surface area [m ² /g]	Si/Al
FD-107	0.217 ^b	0.86 ^b	Y	610 ^b	1.6 ^b
13X APG	0.245 ^a	0.8 ^a	X	686 ^a	1.5 ^a
3A EPG	<< 0.1 ^a	< 0.3 ^a	A	15 ^a	1.4 ^a
CBV100			Y	~900 ^c	5.1 ^c
Me0.X			Y	~900 ^c	5.1 ^c
BEA	0.223 ^a	0.99 ^a	H	631 ^a	150 ^a
MFI		0.6 ^a	NH ₄	> 300 ^a	> 800 ^a
A8x30	1.538 ^a		-	1250 ^a	-
MC14x35	1.909 ^a		-	1200 ^a	-
BAM109			-		-
40_4			-	1250 ^a	-
45_4			-	1000 ^a	-
47_4			-	900 ^a	-
Merck		1–25 ^c	-		-
ZIF-8	0.663 ^c	1.16 ^c	-	1947 ^c	-
Aerogel			-		-

^a value obtained from producer; ^b measured in-house; ^c found by internet research.

Several single point testings of model material impregnated at higher temperature and lower pressure (subcritical; 41–59 °C; 62–68 bar), two testings at higher temperature (supercritical; 56–61 °C; 73–74 bar), as well as one impregnation at a slightly higher temperature and pressure (supercritical; 34 °C, 76 bar) were conducted. Mainly good values (4–13 % change over 14 days) with only one exception (50 % change) were obtained for subcritical conditions. The testing at slightly elevated conditions showed a good value as well (5 % change). Mediocre values (20–24 % change) were obtained for high temperatures and slightly below or above the supercritical pressure. It seems, that very good to good values can be obtained for most tested conditions. A trend can be hardly identified, because of how similar the values are compared to the general variability, and a lack of sufficient data points (both replicates and conditions). The same applies for the influence of impregnation time: data quality and quantity is not sufficient to see any difference between 1, 2, 4 and 8 minutes (**Figure 8**).

Figure 7. Influence of temperature (T) and pressure (p) on the variability over 14 days of FD-107 impregnated with heptane and measured in dry air.

Figure 8. Influence of impregnation time (t) on the variability over 14 days of FD-107 impregnated with heptane and measured in dry air.

Though, no optimisation of impregnation parameters was achieved, a few findings were made: very good to good values (4–20 % change over 14 days) can be obtained by impregnating FD-107, which proves the concept of impregnating porous materials in general, and the influence of impregnation parameters seems to be smaller than the overall variability at least for the model material. Similar values were obtained with conditions above and below the supercritical point of CO_2 . Impregnated FD-107 might be a very good ERM candidate for testings in dry air, but the method should be further improved to completely avoid contact with

humidity. Then it might also be possible to optimise the impregnation parameters. It was decided to focus on non-hygroscopic materials in our project to obtain a better data quality (i.e., less variability) and because the final ERM prototype must function in humid air. The impregnation parameters were maintained at 32 °C and 74 bar.

2.2 Emission testing of different impregnated materials

Porous materials, that are also non-hygroscopic (n.h.), can be activated carbons (AC), zeolites with a high Si/Al ratio or others. Six ACs with different properties were purchased within the project and four of them were tested quite systematically (40-4, 45-4, 47-4 and A8x30) under humid conditions. Similar to the study of FD-107, different impregnation parameters (T and p) were used to investigate any influence on the impregnation of n -hexane and toluene respectively. **Figure 9** shows AC samples, impregnated with n -hexane, according to their p and T coordinates as well as their respective change over 14 days.

Figure 9. Influence of parameters on the change over 14 days (n -hexane) of different activated carbons.

An emission is indeed detectable in humid air for all AC materials, and the overall variability is lower than that of the hygroscopic FD-107. But the change over 14 days is only mediocre (19–42 %). It was found that the repeatability of testing the same impregnated batch is quite good (< 5 % standard deviation), so that the fluctuation in stability must come from the impregnation process and not the testing. Though no trend of p and T can be recognised. The same applies, when impregnating AC with toluene (**Figure 10**). We suspect, there must be parameters, that are not yet fully controlled. One hypothesis is, that pores, especially small and deep pores, are only partially impregnated. Thus, the variability might be indirectly dependent on the porosity if the impregnation

process is not improved. A much longer impregnation time might lead to a full impregnation (equilibrium state). Experiments will be carried out to find and control these parameters. In the meantime, the testing of different material and VOC combinations was continued with standard impregnation conditions. The results are summarised in **Table 6**.

Figure 10. Influence of parameters on the change over 14 days (toluene) of different activated carbons.

Impregnated samples of 40-4 and 47-4 behave more similar than impregnated samples of 45-4 (**Table 6**, entry 4–6). These three ACs were purchased from the same manufacturer and possess a decreasing surface area (**Table 5**, entry 11–13). Thus, the surface area does not explain the similar behaviour between 40-4 and 47-4, but porosity or polarity might be responsible. Interestingly, A8x30 shows slightly worse results (**Table 6**, entry 3), but a considerably smaller variability of changes. This might be due to a bigger pore size compared to the AC 4X-4 materials, and thus less influence of only partially impregnated pores. Two more ACs were purchased but were only tested in dry air yet and will not be further discussed.

Two n.h. zeolites (BEA and MFI) with high Si/Al ratios were purchased as powders (**Table 5**, entry 6–7). Powders can be hardly handled in the autoclave. One solution is to press one gram of powder into a tablet with a diameter of 2 cm, and then impregnating the tablet. This worked well for the BEA material, but not for MFI (tablet too brittle). Mediocre values (heptane: 35–53 %; toluene: 20–42 %; ethylhexanol: 32 % change over 14 days) were obtained with the BEA tablet. Experiments with MFI were postponed until a solution for the impregnation of powders is found. The same applies for powdered AC (4X-4). It was not yet possible to produce stable tablets with these materials.

Table 6. Results of emission testing of different impregnated materials.

Material	VOC	Average change [%]	Dry/humid	n
Me0.25	ethylhexanol	64	humid	1
BEA	heptane	35–53	humid	2
	toluene	20–42	humid	2
	ethylhexanol	32	humid	1
A8x30	hexane	39–42	humid	5
	toluene	34–38	humid	2
40_4	hexane	19–44	humid	8
	toluene	27–46	humid	3
	ethylhexanol	39–47	humid	4
45_4	hexane	36–50	humid	2
	toluene	34–52	humid	4
47_4	hexane	26–43	humid	5
	toluene	24–44	humid	3
	ethylhexanol	40–47	humid	2
ZIF-8	heptane	33–59	humid	8

The polar groups (Al^- centres) of zeolites can be functionalised with CH_3I to lower or even nullify the hygroscopicity. We received three methylated CBV100 materials of different degree (Me0.25, Me0.5 and Me0.75). As the names suggest 25 %, 50 % and 75 % of the polar groups are respectively methylated. The impregnation of these materials turned out to be difficult (high rate of experimental failure), but one testing of Me0.25 succeeded in humid air (ethylhexanol: 64 % change over 14 days). Similar changes over 14 days were found for Me0.X materials in dry air as well. Other testings of hygroscopic CBV100 showed emission in dry air but no emission in humid air.

Two other materials were tested: an aerogel and ZIF-8 (metal organic framework). The impregnated aerogel showed an emission for two days, which quickly decreased below the detection level. We believe the low density and extremely big pore size of aerogel is detrimental for the use as an ERM. The ZIF-8 however showed mediocre values (heptane: 33–59 % change over 14 days). When comparing ZIF-8 and FD-107, which showed very good results in dry air, a few similarities can be seen. Both possess a three-dimensional interconnected pore structure. However, the apertures to the cavities and the cavities itself are different: ZIF-8 has spherical micropores (1.16 nm) and small openings of 0.08 and 0.3 nm diameters,^[2] while FD-107 has cavities of 1.2 nm diameter with bigger openings of about 0.8 nm.^[3] There is no hard limit for molecule and pore size

combinations, because both, the VOC molecules and crystal lattice, are flexible, but the diffusion rate is certainly slower for smaller pore sizes.

Most of the impregnated samples showed only mediocre results of about 20–44 % change over 14 days. The variability remains high, even for n.h. materials. We think the impregnation process is not yet fully controlled. Different parameters such as impregnation time, testing time and surface area will be tested. Especially the impregnation and testing time are promising because we suspect that only partial impregnation takes place, and further stabilisation over time during testing.

2.3 Emission testing of two ERM in one chamber

Besides searching for suitable candidate materials, we conducted testings of two separately impregnated materials in one emission test chamber to see whether the materials affect each other. One possible interaction might be the exchange of VOC between both batches. We took two portions of the same AC (4X-4) and impregnated each with hexane and toluene. Then both separately impregnated batches were put into the same testing chamber. The results can be seen in **Figure 11**. The changes over time and the variabilities are quite similar, when comparing single VOC testing to this simultaneous testing. Maybe the effect is too small to be seen. If necessary, an in-depth analysis of possible VOC exchange could be performed by separating the two batches again after some time, and subsequent single testing in different chambers.

Figure 11. Influence of parameters on the change over 14 days (*n*-hexane and toluene together in one emission test chamber) of different activated carbons.

3 Characterisation of the polymer capsules

The characterisation of polymer capsules sent by FhG involved determination of the capsules' chemical composition, the amount of volatile compounds entrapped within the capsules and investigation of the capsules' shell porosity. For this purpose, various analytical techniques were employed, including thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis, and solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. The measurements were performed on samples after drying at 50 °C in a vacuum oven for different time periods (1 day, 15 days and 30 days). About 150 mg of each sample was used for the analysis.

3.1 FTIR analysis of the polymer capsules

The FTIR spectra of dried limonene-loaded sample GTIL_1 and HDTIL_1 and the FTIR spectrum of the core material are presented in **Figure 13**. The presence of functional groups that belong to polyurethane, polyurea and limonene can be clearly observed. The IR spectra of limonene exhibits characteristic peaks at 2900 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching, $-\text{CH}_3$ group), 1649 cm^{-1} (C-C multiple bond stretching, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$ group), 1432 cm^{-1} (C-H bonding, $-\text{CH}_3$ group), 1400 cm^{-1} (C-H bonding, $-\text{CH}_3$ group). The broad peak at 3345 cm^{-1} is associated with the stretching vibration of N-H bonds in the urethane and urea groups, which constitute the polymer capsule, while the peaks at $1692\text{--}1643\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to typical carbonyl absorption peaks of ester bonds. The peaks at 2900 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of alkane $-\text{CH}$ groups, which form another characteristic group of polyurethane. The presence of non-reacted isocyanate groups could be seen on FTIR spectra of GTIL_1 sample after 1 day of drying, but after 30 days all groups were reacted.

Figure 12. FTIR spectra of toluene loaded samples HDTT_2 (left) and HTIT_1 (right) after drying for different time periods.

3.2 TGA spectra of the polymer capsules

Parallel to the FTIR analysis, TGA measurements were performed with the capsule samples. Comparing the TGA results of samples dried for different periods allows to estimate the amount of VOC within the capsules. Approximately 5 mg of sample were taken for each TGA analysis. However, the specific sample mass is not crucial since the relative mass reduction serves as the primary measurand when determining the amount of VOC.

3.2.1 TGA spectra of GTIL_1

Analysing the TGA spectrum of GTIL_1 reveals five distinct breakpoints of the mass loss curve (blue line, **Figure 14**). The first region, denoted by red dots, spans from 30 to 120 °C and exhibits a mass loss of ~10 %, which could potentially be attributed to the presence of water or other solvents with low boiling points. The second region, indicated by green dots, displays a significant sudden mass loss of about 54 % at 120–173 °C. Subsequently, three additional regions are identified, marked with pink, black, and grey dots. Eventually, at approximately 500 °C, the polymer is completely decomposed, and only a small residue (~4 %) remains. Based on the initial analysis, it is challenging to precisely determine which specific region corresponds to volatile compounds. After 15 days of drying at 50 °C, a second TGA analysis was conducted to assess any changes in the polymer's decomposition behaviour (**Figure 15**).

Figure 14. TGA curve of GTIL_1 sample after 1 day of drying.

In the region marked with red dots, there was only a 3.4 % decrease in mass. This 7 % difference, compared to the first analysis, can be attributed to the evaporation of water from the polymer during the drying period. The region marked with green

dots exhibited a 20 % mass loss. Notably, when compared to the corresponding region in the first analysis, there is a difference of approximately 35 %, indicating that this region corresponds to the evaporation of VOC (limonene), which also agrees with the boiling point of limonene (175 °C). Examining the region marked with pink dots in the first analysis, a mass loss of about 18 % was observed. However, in the second analysis, the mass loss in this region accounted for almost 30 % of the total polymer mass. This seeming increase in mass loss is a result of evaporated VOC due to drying – any minor affected or unchanged mass loss step from before is now relatively increased. This is also true for the regions marked with black and grey dots. It indicates that these regions correspond to the polymer's own decomposition breakpoint temperatures and do not belong to volatile compounds.

Figure 15. TGA curve of GTIL_1 after 15 days of drying compared with the TGA curve after one day of drying at 50 °C.

Figure 16. TGA curve of GTIL_1 sample after 30 days of drying compare with the TGA curves after one and 15 days of drying at 50 °C.

The drying procedure was extended up to 30 days and a subsequent TGA analysis was performed (**Figure 16**). As anticipated, the regions marked with red and green dots exhibit a slight decrease compared to the second analysis. This suggests that the amount of water and volatile compounds in the polymer decreased further. Additionally, the regions marked with pink, black, and grey dots showed a slight increase compared to the second analysis due to the relative increase of polymer. This indicates that the evaporation of VOC during the first 15 days occurred at a faster rate, resulting in a higher loss of mass, whereas during the next 15 days, the evaporation was slower, and the mass loss was lower. Following the third analysis, no further drying was required for another TGA analysis. Instead, a degassing procedure was carried out at 60 °C, utilising the results obtained so far to prepare BET analysis.

3.2.2 TGA spectra of HDTIL_1

The TGA curve of HDTIL_1 also exhibits five distinct breakpoints (**Figure 17**) similar to GTIL_1. The first region, spanning from 23 to 110 °C, corresponds to the evaporation of water. The second region, marked with red dots, displays a mass loss of 30 %, which may be attributed to the evaporation of limonene. The remaining regions marked with pink, green, and grey dots correspond to the deterioration of polymer bonds at different temperatures.

After 15 days of drying HDTIL_1 showed a mass loss of only 24 % in the first region (red dots), while the next mass loss step (pink dots) is about 9 %, which is a slight increase compared to the first analysis. Interestingly, the mass loss steps of these two regions remain the same even after 30 days of drying. It is worth

noting that the mass loss in the pink and green marked areas remains nearly the same across all three measurements. It can be concluded that the region marked with red dots, characterised by a higher mass loss, corresponds to the evaporation of VOC. Since both GTIL1_ and HDTIL_1 exhibit limonene evaporation starting at 100 °C in the TGA analysis, a degassing temperature of 60 °C was selected before conducting the BET analysis. The reason for choosing a lower temperature for the degassing process compared to the observed TGA analysis is that the TGA analysis is conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere, while the degassing process takes place under vacuum. Evaporation increases when lower pressures are applied due to a boiling point reduction.

Figure 17. TGA curves of HDTIL1 at 1st day compared with the TGA curves at 15th and 30th days.

3.2.3 TGA spectra of HTIT_1

Upon examining the TGA spectrum of HTIT_1 on the first day, there is a gradual mass loss observed starting from 31 °C and continuing until 287 °C (**Figure 18**). This slow mass loss is likely attributed to the presence of toluene within the polymer. Beyond 287 °C, there is a sharp vertical mass loss, extending up to 373 °C, which is likely associated with the deterioration of the polymer's main bonds within this temperature range. Comparing this spectrum with the second TGA spectrum conducted after 15 days of drying, there is a slight decrease observed in the first area marked with red dots and the second area marked with green dots. The likely reason for this slight decrease is that during the polymer's formation, a minimal amount of toluene was incorporated into the polymer. As a result, when the polymer is heated, the toluene is slowly released. However, as

the temperature rises beyond 287 °C, both the toluene and the polymer's main structure undergo deterioration. A similar trend is observed after 30 days of drying at 50 °C, indicating a consistent behaviour.

Figure 18. TGA curves of HTIT_1 after one, 15 and 30 days of drying at 50 °C.

3.2.4 TGA spectra of HDTT_2

In the first TGA analysis of HDTT_2, a minimal mass loss of approximately 1.5 % is observed between 25 °C and 200 °C (**Figure 19**). This small mass loss is likely attributed to the presence of toluene and other volatile compounds, such as water, within the polymer. Based on these results, it can be inferred that there is a small amount of toluene present in the polymer. Subsequently, there is a second mass loss of approximately 7 % observed in the region marked with green dots, extending up to 311 °C. However, it cannot be definitively stated that this area corresponds to toluene. Since the boiling point of toluene is around 110 °C, it is expected to have already evaporated from the polymer before reaching 200°C. Therefore, it can be concluded that this region corresponds to the degradation of the polymer's own bonds. Upon analysing the second and third analyses conducted after 15 and 30 days of drying, there are no significant differences observed in the red and green areas compared to the first analysis. After 30 days, the results are almost identical to those of the first analysis.

Figure 19. TGA curves of HDTT_2 after one, 15 and 30 days of drying at 50°C.

3.3 BET analyses of the polymer capsules

After 30 days of drying the capsule samples at 50 °C, TGA results were obtained for the materials. To ensure the removal of any potential contamination and remaining VOC, a degassing process was conducted before performing the BET surface analysis. This step is crucial because if the materials still contain VOC during the BET analysis, it would hinder the device from reaching equilibrium within the required pressure range. The emission of VOC would disrupt the analysis and result in automatic cancellation. Based on the TGA results, GTIL_1 and HDTIL_1 (both samples loaded with limonene) were degassed at 60 °C, while HDTT_2 and HTIT_1 (both samples loaded with toluene) were degassed at 100 °C for a duration of sixteen hours. This degassing process helps eliminate any remaining VOC, ensuring accurate and reliable BET surface analysis. After the degassing process, the samples underwent BET analysis using nitrogen as the probe gas at a temperature of 77 Kelvin. However, due to the inability to completely remove the VOC trapped within the pores of the polymers, even after prolonged vacuum and degassing, the separation of VOC from the polymers continued during the analysis, preventing the generation of a meaningful isotherm graph for nitrogen gas adsorption. It was not possible to obtain a meaningful isotherm graph, thus the calculation of surface area and pore size distribution was hindered. As an alternative approach, considering the low surface area of the polymer capsules, the use of krypton gas was deemed more suitable for measuring surface area, and therefore, the same analyses were repeated using krypton gas. However, due to the desorption of even very small amounts of VOC trapped within

the polymer materials during analysis, it was also not possible to obtain meaningful isotherm graphs for calculating surface area and pore size distribution. Typically, when calculating the BET surface area, a relative pressure range between 0.05 and 0.30 is selected. However, in this case, even within this range, the results are not reliable. For example, when considering GTIL_1 and selecting a relative pressure range of 0.05 to 0.30, it shows a surface area of 0.59 square meters per gram (**Figure 20**). However, this result should be interpreted with caution because, as observed from the isotherm graph, the adsorption curve tends to move towards the monolayer side, indicating the absence of a microporous character. Therefore, in the absence of significant adsorption and a proper isotherm graph, it is not possible to obtain reliable calculations for the surface area and pore size distribution of the materials.

Evaluation of the BET analysis results of the other three capsule samples, it is observed that HDTT_2 shows a similar pattern to GTIL_1 sample (**Figure 21**). On the other hand, HDTIL_1 and HTIT_1 exhibit positive isotherms between relative pressures of 0.0 and 0.65, but the amount of krypton adsorbed is significantly lower than what would be expected from a microporous material. These results, although indicative of low surface area, cannot be considered reliable due to the lack of reasonable isotherm graphs.

Figure 20. BET surface analysis isotherm graph of GTIL_1 sample.

Figure 21. BET surface analysis isotherm graphs of HDTIL_1, HDTT_2 and HTIT_1.

Following the completion of all BET analyses, a final TGA analysis was conducted to compare the results with the TGA analysis performed after 30 days of drying. The aim was to determine whether there were any changes in the temperature breakpoints of the polymers after the BET analysis. This final analysis may provide insights into the underlying reasons for the low BET surface area results of the polymers. Upon reviewing the latest TGA analysis of GTIL_1, it is evident that there are significant mass reductions in the green and red areas (**Figure 22**). This indicates the presence of limonene in GTIL_1, both before and after the BET analysis. It is also noteworthy that the polymer still retains the smell of limonene. However, since the pressure drops to 0.0010 millimeters of mercury during the degassing process and remains constant at this pressure, it cannot be definitively concluded that limonene is present in the polymer. It is more likely that the ten percent limonene observed in the last TGA analysis is due to limonene trapped within the capsule's polymer shell.

Figure 22. TGA curves of GTIL_1 after 30 days of drying and after BET analysis.

Indeed, the TGA analysis of HDTIL_1 shows a similar pattern. There is a 4 % decrease in the red area compared to the previous analysis, indicating some mass loss. However, it is important to note that the remaining 20 % mass persists (Figure 23).

Figure 23. TGA curves of HDTIL_1 after 30 days of drying and after BET analysis.

The comparison between the TGA spectrum of HTIT_1 after 30 days of drying and the TGA spectrum after the BET analysis reveals a remarkable similarity in the TGA curves (Figure 24). This indicates that the area marked with red dots in both

analyses may indeed belong to toluene trapped in the polymer wall, which deteriorates along with the polymer as the temperature rises. Moreover, referring to the first TGA analysis of HTIT_1, it is evident that there was already 9 % toluene present initially if we assume that the red line corresponds to toluene. This result further supports the notion that there was approximately 2 % toluene initially within the polymer, with the remaining portion being trapped in the polymer wall.

Figure 24. TGA curves of HTIT_1 after one and 30 days of drying and after BET analysis.

TGA curves of HDTT_2 after 30 days of drying and after the BET analysis show similar mass loss in the red and green marked areas (**Figure 25**). Referring to the first day TGA analysis of HDTT_2, a 1.6 % mass loss was observed in the red marked area. These results suggest that only 0.4 % of toluene was initially present inside the polymer, while the remaining portion might have been trapped in the capsules' shell.

Figure 25. TGA curves of HDTT_2 after one and 30 days of drying and after BET analysis.

From the examination of TGA results made after one day of drying, it can be observed that the limonene in GTIL_1 constitutes approximately 44 % of the difference between the first and last analyses, and the remaining 10 % is trapped in the walls of the polymer. Similarly, in the case of HDTIL_1, it can be deduced from the TGA measurements that 30 % of the weight is attributed to limonene, with 20 % of this quantity being trapped in the polymer walls. Regarding the TGA results of HDTT2, it is evident that 1.6 % of the mass corresponds to toluene, with 1.2 % of this amount being trapped in the polymer walls. Lastly, based on the TGA measurement results of HTIT1, it can be concluded that 9 % of the mass is comprised of toluene, and 6 % of this amount is toluene that is trapped within the walls of the polymer (**Table 7**).

Table 7. Amount of VOC in polymer capsules estimated from TGA analysis.

Polymer	1.Day		15.Day		30.Day		After BET	
	Red Area %	Green Area %	Red Area %	Green Area %	Red Area %	Green Area %	Red Area %	Green Area %
GTIL1	10 (25-100°C)	54 (120-173°C)	3.4 (25-100°C)	21 (120-173°C)	3 (25-100°C)	20 (120-173°C)	1 (25-100°C)	10 (120-173°C)
HDTIL1	30 (117-166°C)	7 (166-250°C)	24 (117-166°C)	9 (166-250°C)	24 (117-166°C)	9 (166-250°C)	20 (117-166°C)	8 (166-250°C)
HDTT2	1.6 (20-286°C)	7 (200-311°C)	1.5 (20-286°C)	8 (200-311°C)	1.3 (20-286°C)	7.4 (200-311°C)	1.2 (20-286°C)	7.4 (200-311°C)
HTIT1	9 (20-285°C)	76 (286-374°C)	7 (20-285°C)	73 (286-374°C)	7 (20-285°C)	76 (286-374°C)	6 (20-285°C)	78 (286-374°C)

Due to the inability to obtain the desired BET surface areas from the analysis results, it was decided to increase the degassing temperatures and repeat the analyses. For this purpose, a second group of polymer capsules including six samples was sent by FhG to TÜBİTAK. The BET analysis previously conducted on the first group of capsules were repeated by increasing the degassing temperature in the second group of polymer capsules consisting of three samples. The same measurements were repeated four times at different intervals by keeping the capsules (HDTTL_128A, HDTTL_120A, HDTİL_133A) in a vacuum oven at 160 °C for different time periods (1 day, 7 days, 10 days, and 20 days), however the results remained unchanged. The degas processing temperature in the remain group of capsules (GTiL_1, TL_124B, TTL_123B) to 150 °C could not ensure that the VOC (limonene) was completely removed, and the continuous degassing of the VOC during the BET measurements also affected the surface areas of these measurements and result in negative values.

3.4 Solid ¹³C-NMR spectra of the polymer capsules

Solid-state magic angle spinning carbon thirteen NMR technique was used to determine the chemical structures of polymers. Solid NMR spectra were obtained from the remaining polymers after the BET experiments. In **Figure 26** the top NMR spectrum corresponds to the limonene molecule, followed by the hexamethylenediamine and diisocyanate spectra. The bottom NMR spectrum belongs to HDTİL_1. Comparing it with the TGA curve of HDTİL_1 after 30 days of drying, it is evident that approximately 24 % of limonene remained in the polymer, which is clearly observed in the solid NMR spectrum. Furthermore, the peaks corresponding to the reagent molecules are clearly visible. In general, solid NMR spectra tend to have broader peaks due to the density of functional groups within the polymer. However, in the case of these polymers, the peaks appear narrower, indicating that the polymer molecules have a similar size and ordering. Upon comparison of the NMR spectrum of the polymer with the NMR spectra of the reagent molecules, it can be observed that the signals exhibit strong resonance in two distinct regions. The signals between 20–50 ppm correspond to the methyl and ethyl groups of limonene, hexamethylenediamine, and diisocyanate. As these three molecules exhibit peaks in the same region, the signals overlap in this area. Additionally, the signals between 110 ppm and 151 ppm correspond to carbon 1, 6, 8, and 9 of the limonene molecule.

Figure 26. Solid ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of HDTIL_1 after 30 days of drying and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of limonene, hexamethylenediamine, isophorone diisocyanate (including part of Tubassist) and PVA.

In **Figure 27** the solid NMR spectrum obtained from HTIT_1 exhibits typical characteristics of ordinary solid NMR spectra. By overlaying the NMR spectra of the reagent molecules, a spectrum similar to the bottom NMR spectrum is obtained. As mentioned earlier, after 30 days of drying, approximately 7 % of toluene remained inside the polymer. Consequently, the resonance signals of toluene between 140 and 160 ppm exhibit lower intensity compared to the signals of hexanediol and diisocyanate molecules, which can be attributed to the lower amount of remaining toluene within the polymer.

Figure 27. Solid ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of HTIT_1 after 30 days of drying and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of toluene, hexanediol, isophorondiisocyanate (including part of Tubassist) and PVA.

Similarly, upon examining the solid NMR spectrum of GTIL_1 after being dried for 30 days at 50 °C, it becomes apparent that the resonance peaks of limonene exhibit lower intensity between 109–151 ppm (**Figure 28**). On the other hand, the peaks corresponding to diisocyanate and glycerin resonate between 23–70 ppm. This discrepancy in intensity can be attributed to the higher concentrations of the reagent molecules compared to the volatile compound present, causing the peaks of the volatile compound to exhibit lower resonance intensity.

Figure 28. Solid ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of GTIL1 after 30 days of drying and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of glycerine, isophoronediiisocyanate (including part of Tubassist), limonene and PVA.

Upon examining the solid NMR spectrum of HDTT_2, it is evident that the resonance signals of toluene within the polymer are observed between 152–163 ppm. Furthermore, the resonance signals of the reagent molecules exhibit lower intensity between 17–62 ppm. The lower intensity resonance in this region can possibly be attributed to the decomposition of the polymer molecules into varying sizes following exposure to heat. It is normal for peaks to experience a shift of 5–10 ppm in both carbon and proton NMR due to the interactions among atoms within the resulting structure (**Figure 29**).

Figure 29. Solid ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of HDTT_2 after 30 days of drying and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of hexamethylenediamine, isophorone diisocyanate (part of Tubassist), toluene and SDS.

4 Modelling of ERM design

4.1 Definition of the measurand

The specific emission rate is the measurand that will guide the design of ERM. The specific emission rate can be defined for each material and each VOC, as the amount of VOC that leaves the ERM per unit of exposed surface and unit of time. The definition of the measurand will be dependent on the conditions of emission, i.e., the type and conditions of the emission chamber used. The units of the measurand are amount of substance of the VOC being released per unit of time and per unit of surface [$\text{mol VOC min}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$].

4.2 Objectives of the modelling of the ERM design

The VOC mass transfer mechanisms in the ERM involve a series of steps from the VOC reservoir to the sampling point in the emission test chamber. The characteristic time of each transfer step (i.e., resistance to VOC transport)

provides information on the controlling phenomena of a system. The most important step in the transfer of VOC is the slowest step. On the other hand, quick steps can be considered in equilibrium with the slower steps.

The objectives of the modelling of the ERM design are to define the controlling steps and identify the best emission chamber conditions for ERM design. These conditions ensure that the observations of the concentration at the sampling point of the emission chamber give information about the material, with minimal influence of the fluid dynamics inside the chamber.

This objective is accomplished by means of a simplified model based on lumped parameters, including the Biot number as indicator of the ratio of resistance between the internal (ERM) and external (chamber) mass transfer. The results of the model of the ERM design are useful to develop a numerical (FEM) model of the ERM in Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 of work package 2.

4.3 Scopes of simplified model and ERM

The materials investigated in the project represent a modelling challenge in terms of scale. A simplified model to support the design of the developed prototype ERM will provide useful information for decision-making at a low computational cost. The model needs to be fed with information from the experiments so that lumped parameters can be estimated and used to gain insight into the effects of the mass transfer resistance. Having a low computational cost also means a higher flexibility to make decisions on different experiments through quick characterisation of the material.

On the other hand, the numerical FEM model will be used to predict the time dependent VOC emissions from the ERM. The FEM model will be used as seed information on the internal mass transfer of the material (coming from the simplified model) and will combine thermodynamic and physicochemical data to predict the profiles of specific emission rate of the ERM inside different emission test chambers.

Figure 30. Interactions between different models of the ERM and emission test chamber system.

4.4 Realisation of the definition of the emission rate through a simplified model

In systems where transport phenomena are expected between two zones, the pseudo-homogeneous models with lumped parameters help to describe the mass transfer phenomena inside each zone. The feasibility of application depends on whether the observation time (the effective crossing time) is close or not to the characteristic time of the phenomena (zone crossing). If the characteristic time of the zone crossing is much smaller than the observation time, it means the system had the time to go to equilibrium with other phenomena, in this sense, the equilibrium conditions ($\Delta G = 0$) or an interface equilibrium equation can be used as a pseudo-homogeneous model.

4.5 Mass balance of the exposure chamber

The VOC in the outlet of the chamber is coming from a general mass balance that includes two sources of VOC: the ERM and the inlet air stream. Contributions of possible memory effects inside the chamber are considered negligible, as the characteristic time of these kind of phenomena is very short when compared to the long observation time of the emission test.

Assuming the well mixed hypothesis, the molar fraction and temperature can be considered uniform on all the emission test chamber volume, i.e., no gradients of molar fraction and temperature in the chamber, meaning the amount fraction of the sample at the output of the system is the same found in the chamber.

In mathematical terms:

$$\chi_{\{I\}} \cdot \Phi_{mol,I} + R_{ERM} \cdot A = \chi_{\{O\}} \cdot \Phi_{mol,O} \chi_{\{I\}} \cdot \Phi_{mol,I} + R_{ERM} \cdot A = \chi_{\{O\}} \cdot \Phi_{mol,O} + \int^V d\chi PRT dt dV$$

where:

X	Molar fraction	[molVOC/molAir]
ϕ_m	Molar flow rate	[molAir min ⁻¹]
R_{ERM}	Specific emission rate	[molVOC min ⁻¹ m ⁻²]
A	Area of M-C Interface	[m ²]
R	Gas Constant	[J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
T	Chamber Temperature	[K]
P	Chamber Pressure	[Pa]
V	Chamber Volume	[m ³]

Subscripts:

I	Input
O	Output

4.6 Mass balance at the interface between material and fluid

The flow rate is proportional to the driving force (difference of chemical potential), by means of the external mass coefficient. The Mass transfer coefficient is a function of fluid removal from the ERM's surface. In mathematical terms:

$$R_{ERM} = -kc \cdot ((C_O - C_{sat}))$$

where:

R_{ERM}	Specific emission rate	[molVOC min ⁻¹ m ⁻²]
C_O	Concentration at bulk in chamber (output, well mixed)	[molVOC m ⁻³]
C_{sat}	Concentration at the Interface M-C (boundary layer)	[molVOC m ⁻³]
kc	External Mass transfer coefficient	[m min ⁻¹]
R	Gas Constant	[J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
T	Chamber Temperature	[K]
P	Chamber Pressure	[Pa]

4.7 Internal mass transfer of the ERM

The internal mass transfer of the material will depend on the different competing mass transfer phenomena. The level of complexity of this model will depend on the scale of the system and based on the current requirements of the zeolites tested (pores diameter below 101 nm) it could range from molecular (describable by Knudsen) to continuum diffusion (describable by Fick law). In any of these cases, the general balance inside the volume of the material could be described through an effective diffusion term and an equivalent length, as follows:

$$R_{ERM} = f(D_{eff}, L_{eq}, C_o - C_{sat})$$

where:

R_{ERM}	Specific emission rate	[mol _{VOC} min ⁻¹ m ⁻²]
C_o	Concentration at bulk in chamber (output, well mixed)	[mol _{VOC} m ⁻³]
C_{sat}	Concentration at the Interface M-C (boundary layer)	[mol _{VOC} m ⁻³]
D_{eff}	Effective diffusivity	[m ² s]
L_{eq}	Equivalent length of diffusion	[m]

The parameters that describe the internal transport of the ERM will be estimated through regression after the calculation of the external transport coefficient (k_c). To calculate this value, a reference diffusion vial with known internal transport will be used as reference. After characterisation of the chamber, the characterisation of the tested materials can be performed, as well as an optimisation based on the Biot number for specific cases. The specific emission rate of the known vial can be estimated through the following expression:

$$R_{ERM} = \frac{MW_{voc} \cdot P}{R \cdot T} \ln\left(\frac{1 - X_{sat}}{1 - X_o}\right) = \frac{DR_{(t=7d)}}{A_{neck}}$$

where:

R_{ERM}	Specific emission rate	[mol _{VOC} min ⁻¹ m ⁻²]
X_{sat}	Molar fraction at the M-C interface (boundary layer over vial neck tip)	[mol _{VOC} /mol _{Air}]
X_o	Molar fraction inside the vial	[mol _{VOC} /mol _{Air}]
$DR_{(t=7d)}$	Mean diffusion rate over 7 days, calculated through weighing	[mol.min ⁻¹]
A	Area of M-C Interface (neck opening diameter)	[m ²]
R	Gas Constant	[J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
T	Chamber Temperature	[K]
P	Chamber Pressure	[Pa]
V	Chamber Volume	[m ³]

4.8 Evaluation of controlling step

The evaluation of the controlling step is carried out through the estimation of the Biot number. The Biot number is defined as the ratio between the diffusive and convective resistance, as follows:

$$Bi = \frac{k_c \cdot L_{eq}}{D_{eff}}$$

where:

Bi	Biot number	[adimensional]
k_c	External Mass transfer coefficient	[m min ⁻¹]
D_{eff}	Effective diffusivity	[m ² min ⁻¹]
L_{eq}	Equivalent length of diffusion	[m]

4.9 Model implementation

4.9.1 Chamber characterisation

The procedure to characterise the chamber using the simplified model as described in the previous sections follows a series of steps:

1. Design of a diffusion vial as reference for the system.
2. Testing on the vial in the emission test chamber, measuring the concentration profile over time.
3. Using measured data and actual diffusion rate (estimated through weighing) to calculate the internal diffusion, the coefficient of external transport and relative Biot.
4. Improve Biot number by increasing the fan velocity (increasing external transport) so the dynamic in the outlet of the chamber is representative of the dynamic inside the material.

Table 8. Characterisation of BAM 1 m³ emission test chamber.

Parameter	BAM chamber 1	BAM chamber 2	US EPA (Tichenor et al, 1993)
Substance	toluene	toluene	decane
D_{eff} [m ² /h]	0.0052	0.0055	0.021
V [m ³]	1	0.2	0.053
A [m ²]	1.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.021
air ex. rate[h ⁻¹]	0.5	0.5	0.5
k_c [m/h]	2.7	14.3	0.85
Bi	50	253	40

The results from the evaluation of the chamber are presented together with results from the literature where the external transfer coefficient was estimated for some chambers (k_c between 0.85 and 1.5 m/h) and discussed as important parameter for the correct evaluation of internal mass transfer phenomena of the tested materials.^[4]

After characterisation, the emission test chamber 1 broke, so subsequent experiments could not be carried out using the same chamber. Data for the characterisation of the second chamber is available in column "BAM chamber 2". From the results in the **Table 8**, it is evident that the Biot number observed in the smaller chamber is higher and thus more suitable to evaluate the internal transport. Further experiments with a rotating plate were proposed to verify the optimum velocity over which the chamber fluid dynamic conditions have negligible influence over the concentration at the output of the chamber.

5 Conclusion

A decreasing emission profile of $\leq 10\%$ over 14 days was demonstrated for two different capsule types (GTIL and HDTTL) filled with D-limonene. It takes a relatively long time until the capsules reach their stable phase (~ 3 weeks). Unfortunately, impregnated porous materials show changes of 20–45 % over 14 days, when impregnated with *n*-hexane, toluene or 2-ethyl-1-hexanol. Many different tests (such as testing different materials, increasing the surface area of the materials or optimisation of impregnation parameters) were conducted to improve the system. It is unlikely, that the goal will be reached without further adaption to the system (e.g., an additional restriction barrier around the porous material or similar approaches) and that this adaption will be completed within the project. Important properties of the reservoir materials and impregnated porous materials (porosity, size, emission etc.) were measured.

The simplified model was created and fed with data from the characterisation (such as porosity, emission behaviour and chamber parameters), internal validation and additional experiments. One finding is, that the internal transport is the controlling step for the emission from impregnated activated carbon. The FEM model is being developed with the help of the previous FEM model considering the ventilation and chamber size. General new findings are, that the promised goal of $<10\%$ of SER decrease in 14 days is met, if at least one of the following parameters: partition coefficient K , mass transfer coefficient M and diffusion constant of VOC in material D_{mat} is small enough (i.e. much less than its value used in previous study). The variation of other parameters does not influence results significantly.

6 References

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